

Economics of Rice Production in Ibi Local Government Area, Taraba State, Nigeria

Fave. B. Filli

Department of Agricultural Economics and Extension, Federal University Wukari, Taraba State, Nigeria

Helen B. Inyang

Department of Agricultural Economics and Extension, Faculty of Agricultural Sciences National Open University of Nigeria, Kaduna State, Nigeria

Godiya Bulus

Department of Agricultural Economics and Extension, Federal University Wukari, Taraba State, Nigeria

Suggested Citation

Filli, F.B., Inyang, H.B. & Bulus, G. (2023). Economics of Rice Production in Ibi Local Government Area, Taraba State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 1(4), 1201-1212.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2023.1\(4\).110](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1(4).110)

Abstract:

This study focused on the economics of rice production in Ibi LGA, Taraba State, Nigeria. Primary data were collected from 150 respondents through the use of multi-stage random sampling techniques with the aid of structured questionnaire. The statistical tools used to analyze the data were descriptive statistics, profitability model and multiple regression analytical technique were used. The socio-economic characteristics of the respondents indicates that; 52 % were male, 95% were below 60 years of age, 73% were married, 94% had less than 10 persons in their households, 89% had one form of education or the other, 81% had experience of less than 10 years.

The total variable cost of the rice farming was ₦111,140 with labour and fertilizer having the highest share (30% and 29%) respectively, the total fixed cost was ₦32,165, gross margin and gross income was ₦322,445 and ₦465,750 respectively and for every naira invested, 2.25 naira was returned. The regression analysis revealed double-log as best fit with high F-value (196.5) and significant at 1% level and R^2 of 0.872. Age, education, experience, cooperative membership, gender, fertilizer, agrochemicals and labour were significant parameters. Insecurity, poor quality seeds, inadequate finance, pest and diseases, poor storage facilities, and insufficient supply of inputs were the significant parameters affecting rice production at different levels. It is concluded that rice farming in the study area was profitable and viable. It is recommended that rice farmers are to engage in cooperative activities and inputs should be supplied to them in good time for optimum production.

Keywords: *Economics, Rice, Production, Ibi.*

Introduction

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) being the second largest consumed cereal in the world after wheat shapes the lives of millions of people. More than half the world's population depends on rice for about 80% of its food calorie requirements. It has

become a staple food in Nigeria such that every household; both the rich and the poor consume rice (Godwin, 2012). A combination of various factors seems to have triggered the structural increase in rice consumption over the years with consumption broadening across all socio-

economic classes, including the poor. Rising demand is as a result of increasing population growth and income level Global Agricultural Information Network (GAIN, 2012) coupled with the ease of its preparation and storage. Rice has changed from being a luxury to a necessity whose consumption will continue to increase with per capita Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth, thus implying that it is important in the Nigerian diet as a major food item. Despite the relative importance of rice as Nigerian major food and industrial material, the domestic supply is still considered insufficient to match the consumption demand. The local production falls short of the demand (Basorum and Fasakin, 2012) hence, leading to augmentation of shortfall through import. According to Ekeleme et al. (2008), Nigeria consumes 5.4 million metric tonnes of rice annually, of this value, annual domestic output of rice still hovers around 3.0 million metric tonnes leaving the huge gap of about 2 million metric tons to importation. This is consistent with the Daramola (2005) that rice importation in Nigeria is around \$2.2 Billion which is to the detriment of the scarce foreign exchange reserve. This is an unfortunate scenario for a country that is presumed to be the largest producer of rice in West Africa also depending on imports from countries like Thailand, India and USA etc. Rice is cultivated in virtually all agro-ecological zones of the country as it constitutes one major cereal crop produced by Nigerian farmers. It covers both the upland and the swamps, depending on the variety, Kano State Agricultural and Rural Development Authority (KNARDA, 2007). Traditionally, domestic paddy rice production was limited to flooded system until irrigated rice production was introduced with the development of pump irrigation schemes beginning in the mid-1990s; and this has permitted rice area and production to expand at par with population growth in recent years (West Africa Rice Development Association WARDA, 1997). Given the crucial role of rice in the food security of urban and rural households alike, development of rice growing has long been considered a priority in Nigeria. The country has adopted a range of instruments designed to protect and increase local production. The

Nigerian National Rice Development Strategy (NRDS) set up in 2009 aims to make the country self-sufficient in rice by raising production of paddy rice from 3.4 million tonnes in 2007 to 12.8 million tonnes in 2018.

Despite the fact that rice is cultivated almost all the ecological zones of Nigeria, yet its sustainability to mankind still remain small. In 2000, out of about 25 million hectares of land cultivated to various food crops, about 6.37% was allocated to rice production. Rice was grown on approximately 3.7 million hectares of land in Nigeria. Rice production in Nigeria is dominated by smallholder farmers who use traditional methods that are characterized with problems of low productivity (Tsado et al., 2014). Productivity increased in the past four decades is centered on increasing the number of new varieties and a positive and increasing trend in the rate of adoption of modern varieties. Though increase may not wholly be attributed to varietal improvement, the steady increase in rice production in the past four decades provide further evidence that there is potential for further improvement in productivity. It is believed that the access to and adoption of improved rice seed varieties would go a long way in raising the productivity of small-scale rice farmers and consequently improve their livelihood. According to (Adekambi et al., 2009), productivity increase in agriculture has the capability of reducing poverty through increase in farmer's income and reduction in using local farm tools. Nigeria has four rice production systems namely: upland rain fed rice, lowland rain fed rice, irrigated rice and mangrove/deep water rice production system. The international rice market is highly stratified by type and quality thus leaving little room for substitution. There are many varieties of rice and the different varieties are not considered interchangeable, either in processing or in production, with the result that each variety commands a separate market from other varieties. It is common for one variety of rice to rise in price while another one drops in price (USDA, 2000)

In addition to the gap in farming system technology and knowledge, many rice grain producing countries have significant post-

harvest losses at the farm. This is because of poor roads, inadequate storage technologies, inefficient supply chains and farmer's inability to bring the produce into retail markets. A World Bank–FAO study claimed up to 26% of rice produced is lost in developing nations, on average, every year, because of post-harvest problems and poor infrastructure (World Bank, 2011). In Nigeria, rice can be grown in different environments, depending upon water availability. Different rice production systems in Nigeria depend on the ecology and vary in terms of yield per cropped area. The difference between potential and actual yields is very high. However, there is conflicting information on average yields from different sources. (Africa Rice, 2011) reports that in 2008 Nigeria had an increase in rice production of about 31%. In 2012, Africa Rice conducted a diagnostic and yield gap survey to identify the causes of yield gaps and challenges in rice production (Africa Rice, 2013). These two surveys enable the measurement of on-farm yields obtained by farmers and potential yields, which can be determined by crop simulation models and their causes. The major challenges identified from the survey include; weed infestation, lack of availability of purified seeds of new, improved varieties and lack of mechanization. Others include; sub-optimal crop and nutrient management, including timing of interventions in irrigated systems, suboptimal land preparation and water management in rain fed lowlands, and droughts and soil problems in uplands (Africa Rice, 2013). Causes of yield gaps in farmers' fields vary among rice production systems and agro-ecological zones (Africa Rice, 2013). But, typical causes include sub-optimal crop management, yield limiting (e.g. poor soils) and yield-reducing (e.g. pests), factors, socio-economic constraints (e.g. finance, labour shortage) and institutional/ political arrangements (e.g. land availability, rice and fertilizer prices). On this background, the research was to study the economics of rice production in Ibi Local Government Area Taraba state, Nigeria. The study is set to answer the following questions; what are the socio-economic characteristic of rice farmers in the study area, what is the profitability of rice

production in the study area, what are the inputs and output levels of rice production in the study area and what are the constraints in rice production in the study area.

The main objective of the study was on economics of rice production in Ibi Local Government Area of Taraba State. The specific objectives were to; describe the socio-economic characteristic of rice respondents in the study area, estimate the profitability of rice production in the study area, determine the inputs and output levels of rice production in the study area and identify the constraints in rice production in the study area.

Methodology

Study Area

Ibi Local Government Area is one of the 16 Local Governments in Taraba State, with Ibi town as its headquarters. It is located at the southern part of Taraba State and lies within latitude 7° 00' - 8° 10' North of the Equator and longitude 11° 10' - 12° 10' East of the Greenwich Meridian Time (GMT) (Akoga 2012). Ibi has a landmass of 2,728.872 km² with a population of 84, 407 based on 2006 National Population Census. The area shares boundary with Plateau State to the North and Nasarawa State to the West. The southern part bordered to Wukari Local Government Area, while Gassol and Karim-Lamido Local Government Areas had it boarder to the North-East axis. It is located in about 350 meters below sea level and has a plain land all over with fairly undulating and many swampy plain areas of fertile land good for the cultivation of rice, sugar-cane, etc (Akoga 2012). Ibi Local Government Area has a fertile soil. It has River Benue as major river passing through it and its tributaries; rivers Shimakar, Gishiri, Wase and some natural ponds and lakes such as Nwonyo, Isini, Awo, Sai, Aku, Tapga, Baruwana, Akoku, etc. Generally speaking, Ibi Local Government Area can best be described as an agrarian and aquatic environment. Akoga (2012) noted that this description is not an exaggeration considering the enormous farming and fishing activities going on in all the three districts of the

Local Government. The main occupation of the people of Ibi today is fishing, farming and trading. Fishing is the predominant occupation carried out by two major Jukun clans in the town (Wanu and Wurbo). The Hausa are mostly

traders. Types of crops cultivated include rice, maize, millet, guinea corn, cassava, yam, groundnut, bambara nut, benniseed, soya beans, melon, sugar-cane, and among others.

Figure 1. Map of Taraba State showing Ibi Local Government
Source: Geography Department, Kwara University, Wukari

Data Collection

Data was collected using primary data in obtaining information necessary for the analysis. Primary data was obtained by the use of structured questionnaires which will be administered to the respondents. Data collection centered on the socio-economic characteristic of rice respondents in the study area, the profitability of rice production in the study area, the inputs and output levels of rice production in the study area and the constraints in rice production in the study area.

Sampling Procedure

A multistage random sampling technique was adopted in sampling respondents. In the first stage, five wards were randomly selected from the ten wards in the Local Government Area. These wards were Sarkin Kudu I, Dampar I, Nwoyon I, Rimi Uku I and Nwoyo II. In the second stage, five villages each was randomly selected from the five wards making a total number of 25 villages in the sample. In the last stage, six rice farmers were randomly selected giving a total of 150 farmers selected from the sampled villages for the study.

Data Analysis

Both inferential and descriptive statistical techniques were used for the analysis of data that were collected. Descriptive Statistics such as central tendency (mean, median, mode, frequency distribution, percentages) was used.

Multiple Regression Analysis

This was used to determine the various factors influencing the production of rice in the study area. Mathematically the model used in the study is presented in implicit form as adopted by Oke et al., (2007). The explicit functional form (Double-log form) was used as follows:

$$\text{Log}Y = b_0 + b_1 \log X_1 + b_2 \log X_2 + b_3 \log X_3 + b_4 \log X_4 + b_5 \log X_5 + b_6 \log X_6 + b_7 \log X_7 + b_8 \log X_8 + b_9 \log X_9 + b_{10} \log X_{10} + b_{11} \log X_{11} + u \dots \dots \dots 3$$

Where;

Y = Output of rice in kilograms

X₁ = Age of farmers in years

X₂ = Number of household size

X₃ = Education level attained in years

X₄ = Years of farming experience

X₅ = Membership of cooperative organization (Yes=1, No=0)

X₆ = Gender of respondents (Male=1, female=0)

X₇ = Farm size in hectare

X₈ = Quantity of Seeds in kilogrammes

X₉ = Fertilizer in Kilogrammes

X₁₀ = Volume of Agrochemicals in litres

X₁₁ = Labor in man-days

u = error term

Where;

b₀ is a constant term and b₁.b₁₁ were estimated coefficients of the variables, X₁.....X₁₁ are the independent variables respectively, as defined in equations above. The variables X₁-X₁₁ were expected to have positive causal relationships with Y and were added to the model to

determine the extent to which each of them explained variation in total output.

Profitability Analysis

The gross margin is the difference between value of production and the marginal cost of that production. In practice, it is taken as the surplus (or deficit) left after variable costs have been subtracted from value of production or gross income i.e. gross margin is the difference between gross farm income and total variable cost. Gross Margin Analysis will be used as a tool of analysis for this study.

Mathematically it is expressed as;

$$GM = GI - TVC$$

Where;

GM = Gross Margin

GI = Gross Income

TVC = Total Variable Cost

$$GM = TR - TVC$$

$$NFI = TR - TC$$

Where;

$$TC = TFC + TVC$$

$$TR = X_1 P_1 + X_2 P_2$$

NFI = Net Farm Income

GM = Gross Margin

TR = Total Revenue

Results And Discussion

Socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents

The socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents were examined with respect to their gender, age, sex, marital status household size, level of education farming experience, membership of cooperative, source of capital extension worker visit, capital borrowed and farm size as presented in Table 1.

Gender of the respondents

Gender of the respondents showed that majority (52%) of the respondent were male while female

constitute the remaining 48% of the respondent, this implies that male were respondents were the major rice producers in the study area, Gender has a significant factor in rice farming, because of its vital role in determining farming activities which male folks were having the physical fitness to engage in tedious rice activities as compared to their female counterparts. This is in consonance with the works of Onuk et al., 2010; Alam et al., 2014; Angba et al., 2020; Rasaki et al., 2020 and Paudel et al., 2021 who revealed that male were more in agricultural activities in most rural settings.

Age of the Respondents

Age distribution of the respondent revealed that most (95%) of them were 60 years and below, while, only 5% were above 60 years of age. The mean age of the sampled rice farmers' respondents was 37.9 years. This means that the respondents were young energetic persons that were still in their active age. Rice farming need energetic young person's that can face the tedious workforce and attention is needed. This is in line with the finding of Onuk et al., 2010; Alam et al., 2014; Angba et al., 2020; Rasaki et al., 2020 and Paudel et al., 2021 who opined that most farmers in their respective studies were relatively younger in age.

Marital status of the respondent

The result of respondents according to their marital status showed that majority (73%) of rice farmers respondents in the study area were married, 27% of them were not married in one way or the other. The result indicate that majority of the respondent were married and this may be due to the need for them to have more earning to meet up with domestic demands such as feeding, paying school fees and health bills among others in which the unmarried individuals were having less or non. This agreed with the studies of Onuk et al., 2010; Alam et al., 2014 and Angba et al., 2020 that said most farmers were married in their works.

Household size of the Respondents

The result revealed that most (94%) of the rice farmers' respondents have a household size of 10 persons or less, while only 5% of the

respondent have household size of more than 10 persons, with the mean of 4 persons of the respondent have household size between the range of 11-15 while 1.3% has household size of above 15. This implies that more than half of the respondents have household size of less than 5 persons per household. The implication is there will be more need of hired labor to execute farming activities in the study area. This depicts the outcomes of Angba et al., 2020 and Paudel et al., 2021 that showed that most households were relatively smaller in size.

Education level of the respondents

From the result, it revealed that most 89% of the respondents had one form of formal education or the other, while only 11% had no any form of formal education. This implies that most of rice farmers' were educated. Formal education is thought to create a favourable mental attitude for the acceptance of new practices, especially information-intensive and management-intensive practices for effective and efficient performance in rice farming activities and subsequently increase output. This fall in path with the ideas of Alam et al., 2014; Angba et al., 2020; Rasaki et al., 2020 and Paudel et al., 2021 that maintained that most crop farmers had one form of education or the other.

Farming experience of the respondents

The result showed that majority 81% of the rice farmers' respondents had farming experience of 10 years or less, up to 19% of them had experience of over 10 years with the mean of 4.6. This implied that most of the respondents had lesser years of experience and it will possibly have negative effect on the performance of the respondents, and hence respondents with more years of experience will thrive better than the respondents with lesser years of experience in the study area. This follows the submissions of Onuk et al., 2010; Alam et al., 2014; Angba et al., 2020 and Rasaki et al. 2020 that were on the view that most farmers have relatively fewer farming experience.

Table 1. Socioeconomic Characteristics of the Respondents

Item	Frequency	Percentage	Mean
Gender			
Male	78	52.0	
Female	72	48.0	
Total	150	100	
Age			
<30	45	30.0	
31-40	53	35.4	
41-50	33	22.0	
51-60	11	7.3	
>60	8	5.3	
Total	150	100	37.9
Marital Status			
Single	19	13.3	
Widow	11	6.8	
Widower	4	2.6	
Divorce	6	4.0	
Total	150	100	
Household Size			
<5	97		
6-10	44		
11-15	7		
>15	2		
Total	150	100	4
Educational Level			
No Formal Education	17	11.4	
Primary	9	6.0	
Secondary	65	43.3	
Tertiary	59	39.3	
Total	150	100	
Farming Experience			
<5	67	44.6	
6-10	55	36.7	
11-15	12	8.0	
16-20	9	6.0	
21-25	6	4.0	
>25	1	0.7	
Total	150	100	4.6

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Profitability of rice Production

The amount of revenue realized and operating cost of a business venture determines how much gain or loss the enterprise can achieve within a certain period. Gross Margin Analysis was used as a tool of analysis for this study. The gross margin is a dependable analytical tool in determining the profitability of rice production.

It is very useful where fixed capital is a negligible portion of the farming enterprise and is defined as the difference between the gross farm income (GI) and the total variable cost (TVC). Olukosi and Erhabor (2005). The viability of an enterprise is indicated by the amount of profit realized per period of time. Profit is the difference between the monetary value of goods produced and the cost of the resources used in their production.

From the table 2, the total variable cost incurred by the rice farmer respondent was ₦111,140 in which labour and fertilizer incurred the highest cost with 30% and 29% respectively. The fixed cost was ₦32,165 which was discounted on a straight line depreciation formula. The gross income was ₦465,750 which resulted in gross margin of ₦322,445. The return per naira invested was that for every 1 Naira invested a profit of 2.25 Naira is realized that is to say rice production is economically viable in the study area. This sustained the opinions of Abah and Tor 2012; Toluwase et al., 2013; Alam et al., 2014; Ohen et al., 2015 and Ben-chendo et al. 2017 who maintained that crop farming is profitable in their independent studies.

Table 2. Gross Margin Analysis of Rice Farmers' Respondent per Hectare Cultivated

Items	Cost (₦)	Percentage of Variable Cost
Seed	19,750	17.77
Fertilizer	32,150	28.93
Labour	33,050	29.74
Agrochemicals	14,210	12.79
Transportation cost	2,550	2.29
Packaging material cost	9,430	8.48
(A) Total variable cost (TVC)	111,140	100
(B) Total fixed cost (TFC)	32,165	
(A+B) Total cost	143,305	
(C) Gross Income (GI)	465,750	
Gross Margin (GM) (C – A)	322,445	
Return per naira invested (C/B)	3.25	

Source: Field survey, 2022

Regression Result for Respondents

From the results of regression in the table 3 below the selection of the lead equation was based on the comparison of the value of the coefficient of multiple determination (r^2), statistical significance of the coefficient of the variables and the sign of parameters estimated. Meanwhile, the double- log function was chosen as lead equation based on criteria above. The F-value was high (196.5) and significant at 1%, R^2 was 0.872 which 87.2% of the variations in the dependent variable, output were explained by its associations with the independent variables (inputs used) as all variable inputs were age, education level, experience, membership of cooperative, gender and labour were positive and significant at 1% level, fertilizer was positive and significant at 5% level, agrochemical was positive and significant at 10% level, farm size was negative and significant at 5% level. Meanwhile, household size and seeds were not significant at conventional level.

Age of the respondents was positive and significant at 1% level with coefficient of 0.066. This means that an increase in one age by one year will increase rice output by 0.066kg depicting that increase in age of respondents increase experience which will enhance efficiency and effectiveness rice farmers for higher output. Also, age has a significant influence on the decision making process of farmers with respect to risk aversion, adoption of improved agricultural technologies, and other production-related decisions.

Education level of the respondents was positive and significant at 1% level with coefficient of 0.122. This indicate that an increased in the level of education of the respondents would lead to an increase in the output of rice in the study area by 0.122 Kg, in other words, an advancement in educational level of the respondents will lead to a sound increase in rice output in the study area by 0.122kg. This viewed that education aid farmers to adopt new technologies and innovations that will aid farmers' performance and subsequently their output.

Experience of the respondents was positive and significant at 1% level with coefficient of 0.042.

This opined that and additional year of experience by farmers will increase rice output by 0.042kg. This revealed that an addition experience among the rice farmers will improve on farmers' performance through correcting their previous mistakes and weaknesses which will enhance output.

Membership of cooperative of the respondents was positive significant at 1% level with coefficient of 0.066. This depict that rice farmers that were members of cooperative had tendency of increase in their rice output by 0.066Kg as compared to their counterparts that were not cooperative members. This opined that rice farmers' that were in cooperative have opportunities to interact and share knowledge on basics of rice farming which will increase basic knowledge among the respondents, which they will subsequently employ knowledge on their rice farm practice which will improve their output at the long run.

Gender of the respondents was positive and significant at 1% level with coefficient of 0.711. This resolved that, the male rice farmers in the study area have chance of increase of rice output by 0.711Kg as compare to their female folks. This is because male gender has more energy to be involved in the tasking rice farming as compared to their female folks.

Farm size of the respondent was negative and significant at 5% level with coefficients of - 0.054. This unveil that an increase farm size with will decrease output by 0.054kg. This opined that an increase in rice farm size without increase in other corresponding inputs such as labour, seeds, fertilizer, agrochemicals etc will just be waste of land resources which will not have positive effect on the rice output.

Fertilizer applied on rice farm by respondents was positive and significant at 5% level with coefficient 0.450. This indicated that an increase in a kilogramme fertilizer will increase rice output by 0.450kg. This admits that fertilizer as direct source of nutrient and supplement for the growth of rice for maximum output.

Agrochemicals applied on rice farming by respondents was positive and significant at 10%

level with coefficient of 0.028. This suggests that a litre increase in agrochemical will increase rice output by 0.028. This means increases in agrochemicals such as herbicide, insecticide, rodenticide etc will reduce the population of weeds, insect, rodents which interfere with the output of rice.

Labour employed by the rice farmers was positive and significant at 10% level with coefficient of 0.038. This show that an increase

in man-day labour will increase will increase rice output by 0.038. This affirm that labour is a relevant factor in rice farming as most activities involved in rice farming involves physical man labour in which, the more labour employed the more improved the farm management and subsequently the output. This results are in agreement with reports of Onuk et al., 2010; Adeola et al., 2011 and Usman et al. 2014 that identified most of the significant variables as such in their own independent works.

Table 3. Results of Regression Analysis

Item	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t- Value
	B	Std. Error	Beta	
Constant	6.793	0.204		33.219***
Age	0.112	0.039	0.066	2.845***
Household size	0.041	0.026	0.041	1.560 ^{NS}
Education level	0.164	0.026	0.122	6.427***
Experience	0.038	0.013	0.042	3.006***
Cooperative membership	0.131	0.035	0.066	3.734***
Gender	0.695	0.182	0.711	3.821***
Farm size	-0.39	0.017	-0.054	-2.352**
Seed	-0.024	0.016	-0.016	-1.483 ^{NS}
Fertilizer	0.443	0.169	0.450	2.630**
Agrochemical	0.036	0.019	0.028	1.873*
Labor	0.045	0.016	0.038	1.685*
F-Value				196.5***
R-Square (R ²)				0.872 (87.2%)
Source: SPSS,2022				

Note: ***Significant at 1%, **Significant at 5%, *Significant at 10%

Constraints to Rice Production

From the table 4 of constraints associated with rice farming, the result is rank based on the score of the constraints rice respondents faced. The results reveals that insecurity, poor seed quality, inadequate finance, pest and disease, poor storage facility and low input supply were rank high, the implication is that they are the major problem faced by rice farmers in the study area, and the issue of land tenure, market outlet, transportation, flood were rank low, this implies that they have minimal effect on rice production in the study area. According to the studies of Upadhyaya, 1996; Nirmala and Muthuraman, 2009; Sani et al., 2010; Alam et al., 2014; Ibitoye et al., 2014; Dwarikadhish churpal et al. 2015 and Paudel et al., 2021 most of the constraints

identified were also established in their respective works in one way or the other.

Table 4. Constraints Encountered by the Farmers

Constraints	Score	Rank
Insecurity	3.03	High
Land tenure system	2.38	Low
Poor seed quality	3.06	High
Poor market outlet	2.09	Low
Inadequate finance	2.76	High
Pest and disease	2.65	High
Poor transportation system	1.84	Low
Poor storage facility	3.01	High
Insufficient input supply	2.52	High
Flooding	1.96	Low

Source: Field survey, 2022

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study show that rice production was a profitable with gain of 2.25 naira for every naira invested per hectare of land cultivated. The study established that young educated male gender non cooperative members with smaller household and little experience were involved in rice farming in the study area. The regression result showed that F-Value was high (196.5) and significant at 1%, R-square was good (0.872). Among factors influencing rice output in the study area were age, ducation, experience, cooperative, gender, fertilizer, agrochemicals and labour positive and significant, while seeds was negative and significant. Insecurity, poor quality seeds, inadequate finance, pest and disease, poor storage facilities, insufficient supply of inputs, were the major constraints associated with rice farming in the study area.

Based on the findings of this research, the following recommendation were made:

1. Government and non-governmental organization are to support the supply of inputs such as fertilizer, agrochemicals and quality seeds to enhance productivity of rice farmers in the study area.
2. Rice farmers are encouraged to engage in engage in cooperative of their common interest to help them in sharing of ideas on rice farming to improve on scarce knowledge on rice for better output. It will also help them in securing support from governmental and non-governmental organization.
3. Security should be provided to the rice farmer especially around their respective farms for them to be secured from any vulnerability that may affect their life as well as farm product.
4. Extension services on new innovations and technologies should be provided by the farmers for enhancement of their respective output.

References

- Abah, D. & Tor, I. E. (2012). Cost and Returns of Cowpea Enterprise in Lafia Local Government of Nasarawa State, Nigeria. *Production Agriculture and Technology Journal Publication of Nasarawa State University, Keffi*, 8(2), 59-67.
<https://doi.org/10.26765/DRJAFS98201857>
- Adekambi S.A., Diagne A., Simtowe F.P. & Biao G. (2009). *The Impact of Agricultural Technology Adoption on Poverty: The case of NERICA rice varieties in Benin*. International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics (Icrisat), Nairobi, Kenya. Contributed Paper prepared for presentation at the International Association of Agricultural Economists' 2009 Conference, Beijing, China. Africa Rice Center.
- Adeola, S.S., Folorunso, S.T., Gama, E.N., Amodu, M.Y., & Owolabi, J.O. (2011). Productivity and Profitability Analyses of Cowpea Production in Kaduna State. *Advances in Applied Science Research*, 2(4), 72-78.
- Africa Rice. (2011). A New research for Development Strategy for Africa. Africa Rice Centre (Africa Rice) 2012. Africa Rice Centre (Africa Rice). Annual Report 2011: A new Rice research for Development Strategy for Arica. Retrieved from <https://www.africarice.org/files/ugd/0839e4792886b61842451f8bb9a6bddffede79.pdf>
- Africa Rice. (2013). More than Production: policies for Africa Rice Sector. Africa Rice Centre (Africa Rice) 2013. Africa Rice Centre (Africa Rice). Annual Report 2013: More than Production: policies for Africa Rice Sector. Retrieved from <https://www.africarice.org/files/ugd/0839e4ba27bb7e74f34b6e8cc510238254296b.pdf>
- Akoga, N.B. (2012). *Apa-Jukun History in the Benue Valley: A Portrait of Socio-Political History of Ibi from the 19th to 21st Century*. Makurdi: Oracle Business Ltd.
- Alam M.K., Idoko M.D., Musa A.H., Bashir M.B. & Adi S.S. (2014) Economic Analysis of Rainfed Rice Production in Gassol Local Government Area of Taraba State, Nigeria. *Journal of Agriculture and Veterinary Sciences*, 6(2).
- Angba, C. W., Baines, R. N., & Butler, A. J. (2020). Examining Yam Production in Response to Climate Change in Nigeria: A Co-Integration

Model Approach. *Social Sciences*, 9(4), 42. <https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci9040042>

Basorun, J.O., & Fasakin, J.O. (2012). Factors influencing rice production in Igbemo-Ekiti region of Nigeria". *Journal of Agriculture, Food and Environmental Science*, 1, 1-9.

Osugiri, I.I., Osuji, M.N., Ben-Chendo, G.N., Lawal, N.I., & Ibeagwa, B.O. (2015). Cost and returns of paddy rice production in Kaduna State of Nigeria. *European Journal of Agriculture and Forestry Research*, 5(3).

Daramola, B. (2005) *Government Policies and Competitiveness of Nigerian Rice Economy*. Paper Presented at the Workshop on Rice Policy & Food Security in Sub-Saharan Africa Organized by WARDA. Cotonou. and Republic of Benin.

Dwarikadhish C., Koshta A. K. & V. K. Choudhary V. K. (2015). An Economic Analysis of Rice Cultivation and Constraint in Dhamtari District Of Chhattisgarh, India. *Plant Archives*, 15(2), 651-656.

Ekeleme, F., Kamara, A. Y., L.O Omoigui, L.O., Tegbaru, A. Mshelia J. & Onyibe J.E. (2008). *Guide to rice production in Borno state Nigeria*. IITA/Canadian international Development Agency (CIDA), Ibadan. Vol 1. GAIN, 2012

Godwin, U. (2012). Rice farm & milling plant: Sure money spinner. Retrieved from <http://nationalmirroronline.net/new/rice-farm-milling-plant-sure-money-spinner/>

Ibitoye, S. J. Idoko, D. & Shaibu, U. M. (2014) Economic Assessment of Rice Processing in Bassa Local Government Area of Kogi State, Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, 1(2).

Kano State Agricultural and Rural Development Authority (KNARDA). (2007). *The planning in upgrading of Rice Production in Kano State*. A package prepared by Marditech Corporation Sdn. Bhd.Malaysia for KNARDA.

Nirmala, B. & P. Muthuraman (2009). Economic and Constraint Analysis of Rice Cultivation in Kaithal District of Haryana. *Indian Research Journal of Extension Education*, 9(1).

Ohen S.B. & Ajah E.A (2015). Cost and return analysis in small scale rice production in Cross River State, Nigeria. *International Research Journal of Agricultural Science and soil Science*, 5(1), 22-27.

Oke, V.O., Farell, M.J & Ogundele, O.O. (2007), Technical efficiency difference in cowpea production technologies in Nigeria. *World Journal of Agricultural sciences*, 5(5),

Oluyole, K.A., Usman, J.M., Oni, A.O., & Oduwole, O.O. (2013). Input Use Efficiency of Cocoa Farmers in Ondo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Finance and Economics*, 1(1), 8-10. <https://doi.org/10.12691/jfe-1-1-2>.

Onuk E. G., Ogara I. M, Yahaya H. & Nannim N. (2010). *Economic Analysis of Maize Production in Mangu Local Government Area of Plateau State, Nigeria*. Faculty of Agriculture, Shabu Lafia Campus, Nasarawa State University, Keffi.

Paudel, S.; Parajuli, S.; Mahatara, B.; Budhathoki, S. and Kattel, R.R. (2021). Economics of rice production under rice zone in Gorkha District, Nepal. *International Journal of Agricultural and Applied Sciences*, 2(1), 145-150. <https://doi.org/10.52804/ijaas2021.2119>.

Rasaki,W.A., Olojede, M.O., Omotoso, A.B. and Sulaimon, I.O (2020) Economic analysis of soybean production in Ibarapa Zone of Oyo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Underutilized Legumes. Society for Underutilized Legumes*, 2(1), 33–42.

Toluwase S. O. & Abdu-Raheem, K. A. (2013). Costs and returns analysis of cassava production in Ekiti State, Nigeria. *Scholarly Journal of Agricultural Science*, 3(10).

Tsado, J. H., Ojo, M. A. & Ajayi O. J., (2014). Impact of Training the Trainers' Programme on Rice Farmers' Income and Welfare in North Central, Nigeria. *Journal of Advanced Agricultural Technologies, Engineering and Technology Publishing*, 1(2), 157-160.

Upadhyaya, H. (1996) Rice research in Nepal: Current status and future priorities. In *IRRI, Rice research in Asia: Progress and Priorities* (pp. 193-215). Walling Ford: CAB International.

Benny D. Bruton. (2000). 2000 Report. US Department of Agriculture Agricultural Research Service Lane, Oklahoma. Retrieved

from <http://www.lane-ag.org/H2oMelon/watermelon.htm>

West African Rice Development Association (1997). *Rice Production, Marketing and Policy in Nigeria*. Occasional Paper WARDA, Abidjan Cote D'Ivoire. Retrieved from

<https://cgspace.cgiar.org/bitstream/handle/10947/569/wardacpmr4.pdf?sequence=1>

World Bank. (2011). The World Bank Annual Report. Retrieved from <https://elibrary.worldbank.org/doi/abs/10.1596/6/978-0-8213-8828-0>